

Beyond One Million Genomes

D5.2

Roadmap and guidance tool for countries

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Beyond One Million Genomes

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B1MG

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Table of Contents

1. Executive Summary	2
2. Contribution towards project objectives	4
Objective 1	4
Objective 2	4
Objective 3	5
3. Methods	5
4. Results	6
5. Discussion	7
6. Conclusions	8
7. Next steps	8
8. Impact	8
Annex 1. A roadmap for genomics in healthcare	8

1. Executive Summary

Implementing genomic medicine in healthcare services comes with important challenges, including to ensure a highly skilled workforce, a sound legal and ethical framework for data use and sharing, a technical infrastructure for data collection, analysis, and interpretation of genomic data, the public and the patient's trust and involvement, and the equitable access to the important benefits brought by genomic medicine to all citizens. Healthcare systems thus need to manage a complex and interconnected ecosystem, which involves relevant stakeholders, organisations and processes needed to deliver efficient, accessible and equitable treatment, diagnosis and prevention based on genomics. Multiple key areas must be addressed and developed harmoniously to allow for this ecosystem to deliver the best medical care, be sustainable, while allowing for continuous integration of innovation.

In order to guide healthcare systems through the complex process of implementation of genomics in healthcare, the [Beyond 1 Million Genomes](#) (B1MG)¹ project, through its WP on *Delivering Personalised Medicine cross-borders: implementation in healthcare systems and societal impact*, created a playbook entitled "A roadmap for genomics in healthcare". This document addresses issues in the entire chain of value, including technical infrastructure for genomic data, clinical guidelines and infrastructure, ELSI policies, synergies with research and industry, capacity building, economic models and governance, providing pointers to detailed information that can support the implementation of genomics in healthcare systems. The roadmap proposes a series of sequential steps: assess, learn, plan and implement. Starting with assessing the current situation and aimed maturity level of the healthcare system, further learning is encouraged from countries that have considerably advanced in their genomic strategies, and recommendations on experts from the field. The roadmap includes many pointers to best practices, tools and documents with guidelines and recommendations to support the implementation of genomics in healthcare systems.

A *roadmap for genomics in healthcare* is informed by the B1MG [Maturity Level Model](#) (MLM)² ([Deliverable 5.1](#))³, a tool that provides a common matrix for healthcare systems to self-assess their maturity in genomic medicine in eight key areas, and develop a plan for improvement. Results of a pilot using the MLM in eight European countries, allowed the development of a genomic maturity benchmark for each MLM indicator. Three capacity building [Country Exchange Visits](#)⁴ (CEV), organised to countries with established genomic medicine programmes, namely to the United Kingdom, Estonia, and Finland, provide further support to healthcare systems with recommendations and best practice examples. The most relevant outcomes of these CEVs are published in the [Policy Brief](#) (PB)⁵ *Genomics in healthcare: key issues for implementation*, outlining key messages and recommendations for adoption of genomics in healthcare, as well as the videos from the CEVs^{6,7,8,9} and a [report](#)¹⁰. Also included are recommendations on indicators of

¹ <https://b1mg-project.eu/>

² <https://b1mg-project.eu/resources/maturity-level-model>

³ <https://zenodo.org/record/6587561#.ZGTC0OzMirY>

⁴ <https://b1mg-project.eu/resources/>

⁵ https://b1mg-project.eu/images/pdf/Policy_Brief_Genomics_in_Healthcare_2022.pdf

⁶ <https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLweO8RYcVPDOWDmFxRHdEGINsMEubMK5k>

⁷ https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLweO8RYcVPDMTY_Xi0nLSOtD67jeydIJ7

⁸ <https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLweO8RYcVPDM5ydSVQuOO7WBpkZm8dycy>

⁹ https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLweO8RYcVPDM9Bo_safKw9bQDWueEx6ZA

¹⁰ <https://b1mg-project.eu/images/pdf/B1MG%20WP5%20Country%20Exchange%20Visit%20Report.docx.pdf>

economic viability for the integration of genomics into healthcare in European countries ([Deliverable 5.3](#)¹¹, [HEOR Recommendations](#)¹², [HEOR Summary Brief](#)¹³). Pointers to the recommendations and guidelines from the [1+MG Framework](#)¹⁴, developed by the B1MG project, examples of best practices and outputs from other projects under the umbrella of the International Consortium for Personalised Medicine ([ICPerMed](#))¹⁵ as well as guidelines from the Global Alliance for Genomic Health ([GA4GH](#))¹⁶ are also included.

This roadmap is therefore a very comprehensive guide to the current status of the field of genomic medicine in healthcare, covering all crucial areas with the most up to date recommendations for genomic medicine in healthcare.

2. Contribution towards project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following objectives/key results:

	Key Result No and description	Contributed
Objective 1 Engage local, regional, national and European stakeholders to define the requirements for cross-border access to genomics and personalised medicine data	1. B1MG assembles key local, national, European and global actors in the field of Personalised Medicine within a B1MG Stakeholder Coordination Group (WP1) by M6.	No
	2. B1MG drives broad engagement around European access to personalised medicine data via the B1MG Stakeholder Coordination Portal (WP1) following the B1MG Communication Strategy (WP6) by M12.	No
	3. B1MG establishes awareness and dialogue with a broad set of societal actors via a continuously monitored and refined communications strategy (WP1, WP6) by M12, M18, M24 & M30.	No
	4. The open B1MG Summit (M18) engages and ensures that the views of all relevant stakeholders are captured in B1MG requirements and guidelines (WP1, WP6).	No
Objective 2 Translate requirements for data quality, standards, technical infrastructure, and ELSI into technical specifications and implementation guidelines that captures European best practice	Legal & Ethical Key Results	
	1. Establish relevant best practice in ethics of cross-border access to genome and phenotypic data (WP2) by M36	No
	2. Analysis of legal framework and development of common minimum standard (WP2) by M36.	No
	3. Cross-border Data Access and Use Governance Toolkit Framework (WP2) by M36.	No
Technical Key Results		

¹¹ <https://zenodo.org/record/8183336>

¹² <https://b1mg-project.eu/images/pdf/1+MG%20HEOR%20workshop%20summary%20brief.pdf>

¹³ <https://b1mg-project.eu/images/pdf/1+MG-HEOR-Summary-paper.pdf>

¹⁴ <https://framework.onemilliongenomes.eu/>

¹⁵ <https://www.icpermed.eu/>

¹⁶ <https://www.ga4gh.org/>

	4. Quality metrics for sequencing (WP3) by M12.	No
	5. Best practices for Next Generation Sequencing (WP3) by M24.	No
	6. Phenotypic and clinical metadata framework (WP3) by M12, M24 & M36.	No
	7. Best practices in sharing and linking phenotypic and genetic data (WP3) by M12 & M24.	No
	8. Data analysis challenge (WP3) by M36.	No
	Infrastructure Key Results	
	9. Secure cross-border data access roadmap (WP4) by M12 & M36.	No
	10. Secure cross-border data access demonstrator (WP4) by M24.	No
Objective 3	1. The B1MG maturity level model (WP5) by M24.	Yes
Drive adoption and support long-term operation by organisations at local, regional, national and European level by providing guidance on phased development (via the B1MG maturity level model), and a methodology for economic evaluation	2. Roadmap and guidance tools for countries for effective implementation of Personalised Medicine (WP5) by M36.	Yes
	3. Economic evaluation models for Personalised Medicine and case studies (WP5) by M30.	No
	4. Guidance principles for national mirror groups and cross-border Personalised Medicine governance (WP6) by M30.	No
	5. Long-term sustainability design and funding routes for cross-border Personalised Medicine delivery (WP6) by M34.	No

3. Methods

The concept for the present roadmap was developed through discussion among experts from the B1MG WP5, *Delivering Personalised Medicine cross-borders: Implementation in Healthcare systems and Societal Impact*. We sought for a format that would be simple to use, yet informative for healthcare systems establishing their genomic strategies, and that could be updated regularly. We further wanted to base the roadmap on the framework previously developed within B1MG for the MLM for genomics in healthcare, namely its key domains, and incorporate up to date guidelines, best practices and recommendations from the 1+Million Genome Initiative as well as other initiatives in Europe and globally .

After a series of brainstorming sessions, the concept was set as a playbook entitled *A roadmap for genomics in healthcare*. This is a graphical document designed to provide healthcare systems with pointers to guidance documents and tools. The aim of the playbook is to support assessment and the learning steps of a process that will be conducive to implementation of genomics in healthcare systems. This is done by integrating tools, best practices, standards,

guidelines or recommendations, developed through the actions of the B1MG WP5, namely the B1MG MLM ([Deliverable 5.1](#)¹⁷), the CEVs, the outcomes of meetings and workshop on economic models methodology for genomics ([Deliverable 5.3](#)¹⁸), and other supporting documents integrated in the 1+MG Trust Framework. Additionally, it incorporates relevant documents developed by other important initiatives in the area of genomics for health and personalised medicine (eg, ICPeMed, GA4GH). The selection of documents was based on the MLM key Domains, and is intended to be regularly updated with novel information.

4. Results

A roadmap for genomics in healthcare was developed as a playbook to support the implementation of genomics in healthcare systems throughout Europe. This playbook suggests a process of Assessment and Learning steps guiding Implementation, and is based on previous work carried out by the B1MG WP5, namely the B1MG Maturity Level Model (MLM), as well as a number of capacity building initiatives, including country exchange visits, webinars and workshops.

The first step of Assessment is grounded on the MLM, as a tool that provides a common matrix for healthcare systems to assess the maturity of their use of genomics, across a number of key domains. The MLM was tested in a real world setting as a pilot exercise by healthcare systems in eight European countries (see [Deliverable 5.1](#)¹⁹). The results from this pilot highlighted common maturity strengths and weaknesses, as well as maturity asymmetries across countries. A benchmarking system has been established and is included in the roadmap for users seeking to level up their maturity with other healthcare systems.

Assessment is followed by a Learning step, which is provided as a comprehensive collection of pointers to relevant documents in each of the MLM key domains, produced by B1MG WP5, other work packages from B1MG/1+MG working groups, and also other European and international initiatives like the International Consortium of Personalised Medicine (ICPeMed) or the Global Alliance for Genomic Health (GA4GH). These documents are diverse, including for example guidelines, best practice examples, standards, scientific articles, white papers and other. As examples, the three Country Exchange Visits (CEVs) to countries with advanced genomic medicine programmes organised by the B1MG WP5, namely the United Kingdom (UK), Estonia, and Finland provided a wealth of up to date information on genomic medicine programs and main stakeholders in these countries. Also included are recommendations on health economic models developed by the B1MG WP5/+MG WG6, as well as documents associated with the [1+MG Framework](#)²⁰ on ELSI, data quality, data standards, and the technical infrastructure for data access.

Other initiatives, namely the [ICPeMed](#)²¹ and the [GA4GH](#)²², actively fostering and supporting research in personalised medicine and its implementation in healthcare, have produced a set of best practices, guidelines and documents that complement the learning step of the Roadmap.

¹⁷ <https://zenodo.org/record/6587561#.ZGTC00zMIrY>

¹⁸ <https://zenodo.org/record/8183336>

¹⁹ <https://zenodo.org/record/6587561#.ZGTC00zMIrY>

²⁰ <https://framework.onemilliongenomes.eu/>

²¹ <https://www.icpermed.eu/>

²² <https://www.ga4gh.org/>

ICPerMed was formally established in 2016, and now connects more than 40 European and international institutions, with the support from the European Commission. ICPerMed supports research and implementation of Personalised Medicine (PM) in Europe and internationally, developing strategic documents²³, carrying out mapping activities and publishing Best Practices in a wide range of PM-related areas across Europe. Furthermore, the ICPerMed Family of Coordinating and Support Actions are producing valuable recommendations on topics of major relevance for research and implementation of Personalised Medicine. GA4GH, established in 2013, is a not-for-profit international association that works towards expanding genomic data use within a human rights framework, producing standards and guidelines, in areas that are key to genomic medicine effective implementation in healthcare²⁴. Particularly relevant are the documents, standards and guidelines aiming to enable a trustful environment for data use. These documents cover areas that span the domains of the [MLM](#)²⁵, namely ethical and legal issues, clinical organisation, tools and standards, infrastructure for the use of quality FAIR data, guidelines for research studies to synergise with clinical outcomes, and public engagement.

The playbook is designed to be available online, within the 1+MG website, and to be regularly updated as a repository of up to date information that can be helpful for healthcare systems seeking to establish or optimise their use of genomics.

The playbook is found in Annex 1.

5. Discussion

Despite the advances in genomic medicine, it is clear that there are asymmetries in healthcare implementation across Europe. These need to be overcome to provide European citizens with equal access to the best genomic medicine.

The MLM instrument has proven useful in identifying the current maturity of healthcare systems regarding the use of genomics, and providing a path forward. It is important to note that the MLM domains shown, by the pilot study, as requiring particular investment in all countries ([Deliverable 5.1](#)) coincide with the key recommendations provided by the CEVs as critical to deliver personalised medicine to society ([Policy Brief](#)). This is relevant because it highlights the usefulness of the MLM tool, to support European healthcare systems in maturity assessment and developing strategies for genomic medicine. The MLM is therefore validated as a basis for the Assessment step in the roadmap for genomics in healthcare. The Benchmarking tool is further used to help healthcare systems understand how they are performing compared to the median maturity of other health systems. The benchmarking of maturity will thus promote sharing of best practices in a continuous improvement effort.

The Learning step is organised following the MLM Key Domain structure, and provides pointers to documents relevant for the indicators covered in each Domain. These include the recommendations, guidelines, standards and tools produced by B1MG and collectively denominated as the 1+MG Trust Framework. Overall, the 1+MG Trust Framework provides

²³ https://www.icpermed.eu/media/content/Vision_Paper_2019.pdf

²⁴ <https://www.ga4gh.org/document/strategic-roadmap-2020/>

²⁵ <https://b1mg-project.eu/resources/maturity-level-model>

assurance regarding the quality of the practices for genomic data generation, governance and access, including ELSI, data quality, data standards, and technical infrastructure standards. Guidance on this quality assurance is extremely relevant for genomics in healthcare.

In addition, outputs from other initiatives, like ICPeMed, and GA4GH, are also incorporated in the Learning step as they complement the 1+MG Trust Framework recommendations, guidelines and tools. In this way, this roadmap becomes a tool for global use by healthcare systems, as it incorporates not only best practices and standards established and recommended internationally, but covers all the key domains for a sustainable implementation of genomics and, ultimately, personalised medicine in healthcare.

6. Conclusions

The 1+MG initiative set the goal of enabling access to genomic data and linked personal health data across European countries. For this purpose, a federated secure cross-border infrastructure and a framework of guidelines, standards and best practices are under development, providing a major contribution for genomic medicine. By promoting and facilitating the adoption of genomics by healthcare systems, the 1+MG will also impact how European citizens benefit from the widespread use of personalised medicine. The B1MG project, through the activities of the WP5, contributed to push Europe closer to achieving this goal. This roadmap integrates outputs of the B1MG activity on healthcare implementation, the 1+MG Trust Framework and outputs from other relevant initiatives, to assess, plan and implement genomics into healthcare.

7. Next steps

The playbook will be available through the 1+MG website, together with the MLM toolkit and benchmark, and the components of the 1+MG Trust Framework. The MLM benchmark and the pointers to relevant documents will be updated regularly.

8. Impact

The level of participation in the CEVs and the MLM pilot evidence the genuine interest that exists among European countries and stakeholders relative to healthcare implementation. There was also a clear commitment to invest in a network for sharing best practices that promote the implementation of genomics in healthcare as a collaborative effort in Europe. This roadmap puts together relevant information that will be valuable for healthcare systems in European countries, in a simple format, with the advantage of being a live document with regular updates.

Annex 1. A roadmap for genomics in healthcare

The roadmap can be found [here](#) as well copied below:

A Roadmap for Genomics in Healthcare

Implementation of genomic medicine in healthcare

The implementation of genomic medicine in healthcare systems will bring us closer to making personalised medicine a reality, with major socioeconomic benefits.

Through genomic medicine, citizens and patients will be able to widely benefit from genomic data analysis for accurate and timely diagnosis, more effective treatments with fewer adverse events and, in the near future, accurate profiling for disease prevention.

However, implementation of genomics in healthcare is complex and requires adjustments in the governance, structure and organisation of health services, as well as dedicated investments. Moreover, the progress of implementation varies with country context.

Facilitating dialogue and cooperation among countries for capacity building and sharing of best practices is therefore key to promoting equity in access to Personalised Medicine (PM) across Europe.

Development of a Roadmap for Genomics in Healthcare

This roadmap was developed in the context of the [1+Million Genomes](#) (1+MG) initiative activities to promote the societal impact of genomic medicine. It is based on shared knowledge and experience from experts, in various crucial areas of genomic medicine, across Europe and beyond.

The roadmap is supported by the 1+MG Maturity Level Model (MLM) framework. This 1+MG MLM is a tool for health systems to self-assess their maturity level regarding the implementation of genomics in healthcare, and to define a path to optimization according to a common matrix.

As such, the 1+MG MLM aims to promote and facilitate the adoption of genomics in clinical practice, close equity gaps in access across Europe, and make personalised medicine accessible to all citizens and patients in Europe.

Roadmap steps

ASSESS - the 1+MG Maturity Level Model

What is it?

The 1+MG MLM is a tool for healthcare systems to self-evaluate the level of maturity of their genomic medicine practices according to a common matrix, and to define a path to optimization.

How?

The MLM assesses indicators in eight key domains for the implementation of genomics in healthcare. Maturity of indicators in each domain is assessed by selecting one of five predefined levels for each indicator.

The five maturity levels are indicative of a maturity progression, from a non-existent or *Ad hoc* level of implementation to a high level of maturity, characterized by a system fully adopted by the healthcare system, adaptable to opportunity and change, and in support of international cooperation.

Using the Maturity Level Model

Identify stakeholders and assemble an assessment team of multidisciplinary experts from the Ministry of Health and other relevant national or regional agencies.

Following the [User guide](#) and [Glossary](#), and using the Assessment Tool, perform the self-assessment by building consensus on the maturity level of the indicators in each of the MLM domains, based on the evidence gathered by the assessment team.

Analyse the assessment outcomes, identify strengths, weaknesses and areas for improvement.

Develop an Action Plan: define current and desired maturity status and a path towards optimization with support from this roadmap.

Using the Maturity Level Model

Maturity assessment example – Domain 1: Governance and Strategy

Indicator	ML1	ML2	ML3	ML4	ML5
Governance: Country/region has dedicated governance for genomics in healthcare	No dedicated governance for genomics in healthcare	Elements of governance exist but are not fully functional	Scope of governance for genomics has been defined but elements are still under development	There is a governance body that is fully operating, led centrally, and activities are monitored based on a work plan	Governance body is institutionalised, recognised as the lead for genomics in healthcare, and is open to novel developments and supportive of international cooperation
Priority: Genomics in healthcare is established as a priority at national/regional level	Genomics in healthcare is not included in national/regional health plans	Inclusion of genomics in healthcare in relevant national/regional health plans is under discussion	Genomics in healthcare is included in relevant national/regional health plans	Genomics in healthcare is implemented as part of national/regional health and other relevant plans (e.g. education, research)	Genomics in healthcare is implemented in health and other relevant plans, and is periodically evaluated for optimisation, taking into account novel developments at the international level
Strategy: There is a national/regional strategy for genomics in healthcare with an implementation plan	No genomics in healthcare strategy with costed implementation plan	A strategy for genomics in healthcare with costed implementation plan is under discussion	A costed implementation plan for genomics in healthcare is developed and approved	The national/regional strategy for genomics in healthcare is under implementation	The national/regional strategy for genomics in healthcare is implemented, with monitoring and long term resources and aligned with European and international strategies

Visit the MLM here

ASSESS - Benchmarking

MLM in real-life settings

The 1+MG MLM has been used by eight European countries in a pilot exercise, to establish the maturity levels of genomic medicine in their healthcare systems: Belgium, Denmark, Finland, Ireland, Italy, Lithuania, Portugal, and Spain.

The maturity level assessment of these healthcare systems was fundamental for identifying areas of investment, exchanging best practices and harmonising procedures, towards bridging development gaps across Europe and achieving equity in access to Personalised Medicine for all citizens.

Mapping maturity in Europe

The pilot exercise allowed the identification of common European strengths and weaknesses in the MLM domains, as well as maturity asymmetries across Europe.

Benchmarking maturity

Benchmarking the MLM allows healthcare systems to understand how they are performing compared to the maturity of other systems, for each indicator in the eight MLM domains. The benchmarking of maturity will promote sharing of best practices in a continuous improvement effort.

ASSESS - Benchmarking: an example

Benchmarking maturity

The results from the maturity level assessment of a healthcare system can be submitted online for benchmarking, using the Benchmarking Tool, as exemplified here for the indicators of Domain I.

Submission of maturity assessment

Domain I - Governance and strategy

I1 - Country/region has a dedicated governance for genomics in healthcare

I2 - Genomics in healthcare is established as a priority at national/regional level

I3 - There is a national/regional strategy for genomics in healthcare with a costed implementation plan

Submit For each Domain I indicator, select and submit the attributed score, from a scale of 1 to 5.

For each indicator, the Benchmarking Tool will provide users with the percentage distance between their maturity level score (pink) and the highest maturity score (blue) among all submitted health systems, for that indicator. This information is accessible for each domain, exclusively by the submitters, using a private link.

Distance to top score

Distance to top score (%) is calculated (for each indicator) as $\frac{\text{Top score} - \text{Score submitted}}{\text{Top score} - \text{Minimum score}} \times 100$, minimum score being 1.

The overall relative frequency of maturity levels from all contributing health systems, for each indicator in every Domain, will be available publicly as dashboard. This will provide a graphical interface with at-a-glance view of maturity levels across Europe. Health system contributions will be anonymous.

LEARN, PLAN & COMMIT

- Learn from country exchange visits

- Exchange of best practices and experiences is fundamental for equitable access to genomic medicine for every citizen across Europe.
- Three Country Exchange Visits (CEV) carried out by the [Beyond One Million Genomes](#) (B1MG) project led to [Policy Recommendations on Key Issues for Genomics in Healthcare](#), providing guidance to build efficient and sustainable genomic medicine strategies:
 1. Patient and citizens trust and engagement are critical aspects for a fair and valuable implementation of genomic medicine
 2. Infrastructure for implementation of genomics in clinical practice requires a safe and trusted environment for collection and use of genomic and health data
 3. Ethical and legal frameworks are needed to ensure secure and transparent data collection, analysis and use, protecting citizens' and patients' rights
 4. Training of healthcare professionals guarantees a competent and knowledgeable workforce
 5. Synergies among healthcare, research and industry benefit citizens and patients, healthcare services, health economy and society at large

Country Exchange Visits

– United Kingdom recommendations

- Political support is a powerful enabler for the implementation of genomics in healthcare.
- The concept of a learning healthcare system was implemented to ensure that results from routine genomic testing done within the National Health System (NHS) would feed back into research.
- A well informed and engaged workforce requires investment in developing professionals, such as genetic counsellors, and new professions, like clinical scientists, and medical informaticians.

[Watch the UK Country Visit](#)

Country Exchange Visits – Finland recommendations

- The National Genome Centre is the public authority responsible for the Finnish population genome database, promoting equity and the responsible use of genomic data.
- The Finnish Health Sector Growth Strategy has a political commitment of ministries from diverse sectors.
- A strong legal and ethical framework to ensure citizens' trust is a priority.
- A stable collaboration between healthcare, research and industry, recognises the private sector as a valuable partner.

[Watch the Finland Country Visit](#)

Country Exchange Visits – Estonia recommendations

[Watch the Estonia Country Visit](#)

- A health portal links multiple electronic databases, including clinical diagnosis, prescription and billing, in a central technical infrastructure.
- Long-term investment in communication campaigns resulted in widespread public support, with a significant percentage of the Estonian population represented in the national Biobank and expecting benefits from genomic data use.
- The Human Genes Research Act provides a legal framework dating back to 2000 when its national Biobank was established.

LEARN, PLAN & COMMIT

- Use available guidelines and best practices to optimise the use of genomic medicine in healthcare systems

Domain I. Governance & Strategy

Guidance from 1+MG and other initiatives related to Personalised Medicine

- Policy Brief: Genomics in healthcare: key issues for implementation
- Country Exchange Visit (CEV) Report
- CEV to the UK: Genomics in the UK - a tale of research and healthcare
- CEV to Estonia: Governance of personalised medicine in Estonia
- CEV to the UK: Implementing genomics in the NHS
- ICPeMed Publications
- ICPeMed Vision Paper
- ICPeMed Best Practices Implementation Examples
- SRIA on PM (EP PerMed)
- Danish strategy for personalised medicine
- Genomic Medicine France 2025
- Genome strategy Finland
- Genome UK implementation plan
- Genomics England
- Australia Genomics

Domain II. Investment and economic models

Guidance from 1+MG and other initiatives related to Personalised Medicine

- CEV to the UK: Genomics England, a strong collaboration with the NHS
- 1+MG policy brief: Recommendations from the 1+MG HEOR workshop
- 1+MG workshop summary paper: Review of EU initiatives related to the implementation of whole genome sequencing into clinical practice
- B1MG Deliverable D5.3: Economic models methodology and case studies
- HEcoPerMed
- Short scenarios for future PM (HEcoPerMed)
- Health economic perspective on PM (HEcoPerMed)
- Case studies on health economic modelling (HEcoPerMed)

Domain III. Ethics, legislation and policy

Guidance from 1+MG and other initiatives related to Personalised Medicine

- 1+MG Framework on ELSI issues
- B1MG Resources
- CEV to Finland: Legislation-authorisations for companies/research groups to use genomics data
- Regulating the unknown, a guide to regulating genomics for health policy-makers
- GA4GH guidance products
- GDPR EU
- EHDS
- TEHDAS
- UK Biobank

Domain IV. Public awareness and acceptance

Guidance from 1+MG and other initiatives related to Personalised Medicine

- CEV to the UK: Patient engagement-every data point has a face
- B1MG Deliverable 1.6: Citizen engagement and public trust in genomic data sharing
- B1MG Deliverable 1.5: Stakeholders trust in genomic data sharing landscape analysis
- Policy brief: key issues for implementation of genomics
- B1MG poster: Recommendations for trustworthiness from an experts workshop organised by B1MG
- Engaging patients and the public GA4GH
- Involving patients with CV diseases (ICPerMed)
- NAGEN 1000 (ICPerMed)

Domain V. Workforce skills and organisation

Guidance from 1+MG and other initiatives related to Personalised Medicine

- CEV to the UK: Training and tools in genomics for the entire healthcare workforce
- Education in pharmacogenomics (ICPerMed)
- NAGEN 1000 (ICPerMed)
- Genomic testing: a competency framework
- Genomics Education Program
- Instituto Roche: Competencies for healthcare professionals in personalised medicine (spanish)

Domain VI. Clinical organization infrastructure and tools

Guidance from 1+MG and other initiatives related to Personalised Medicine

- CEV to the UK: Genomics England, a strong collaboration with the NHS
- CEV to Finland: The FinnGen project: opportunities for discoveries and translation
- CEV to Finland: 1+MG-the role and perspectives of industry in genomics
- CEV to Estonia: Private sector in personalized medicine in Estonia, government's view
- PERMIT Project (ICPerMed)
- PERMIT recommendations (ICPerMed)
- Pharmacogenetics-based clinical decision (ICPerMed)
- Adoption of EMR (ICPerMed)
- PERSEPHONE project and multidisciplinary teams (ICPerMed)
- Institutional synergies for lung cancer (ICPerMed)

Domain VII. Clinical genomics guidelines and infrastructure

Guidance from 1+MG and other initiatives related to Personalised Medicine

- B1MG resources
- 1+MG Framework sequencing guidelines
- GA4GH products
- Genomic centers, example from Germany (ICPerMed)
- CPIC guidelines
- Dutch pharmacogenetics working group Guidelines
- PharmGKB resources
- ACMG guidelines
- ClinVar
- ClinGen

Domain VIII. Data management, standards and infrastructure

Guidance from 1+MG and other initiatives related to Personalised Medicine

- 1+MG recommendation: Recommendations for a Data Access Governance Framework
- B1MG Proof of Concept: Federated data access rare diseases proof of concept
- 1+MG Framework technical infrastructure
- 1+MG Framework data standards
- Data connect API (GA4GH)
- Interoperable data, the Swiss example (ICPerMed)
- Resource Entitlement Management System REMS
- Life Science AAI
- Federated EGA (FEGA)
- Htsget protocol

Implementation

This roadmap, with assessment and suggested guidance documents, will help health systems define the roadmap towards implementation of genomics into healthcare. The MLM domain indicators and corresponding maturity levels will also provide support to monitor progress along the path to higher maturity.

This process can be an iterative process. The MLM is designed to be performed at regular intervals, consistently assessing the advancement over time, helping to identify areas of strength and potential bottlenecks, as well as solutions. This roadmap is intended to be a living document, regularly updating sources of guidance overtime. It thus offers the opportunity to continually access up to date best practices from the international community.

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